

“DETERMINATION OF A-AMYLASE ENZYME, ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY, ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY USING CERTAIN MEDICINAL PLANTS”

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Abstract

The Inhibition of carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzymes such as α -amylase in patients with type II diabetes can be an important strategy in the level of blood glucose after a meal, plants for α -amylase inhibition contains various chemical constituents with potential and therefore therapeutic use possible. Nine types of plants include (Clove, Lemon, Chamomile, Radish, Ginger, Black seed, pomegranate, Beetroot and Garlic) were used in this study to select the optimum plant material that inhibited α - amylase enzyme. Raphanus raphanistrum was chosen, it had the highest inhibition activity of the enzyme (95.5%). Also sodium phosphate buffer (0.2 M, pH 7.5) was selected as a best extraction buffer of plants inhibitor with inhibition activity 83%. The optimum extraction ratio represented by 1:20 (w:v) after 90 min, it was given 96.8% enzyme inhibition activity. Antioxidant activities of plants were performed using DPPH free radical scavenging assay, and lemon had a highest by 94.4%. This confirms that the plant might protect cells from oxidative damage, resulting in certain diseases.

Keywords: plant materials, diabetes mellitus, TPC, antimicrobial agents

INTRODUCTION: Amylase plays a wide range of biotechnological applications in food industry, fermentation, textile and paper industries and having above 25% demand on a global scale. Amylase has been used successfully in starch saccharification, brewing and distilling industries. Presently, amylase production has reached up to 65% of the world market and continuously increasing the usage . α -amylases have been derived from various sources such as plants, animals and microorganisms. Microbial amylase meet industrial demand as there is a possibility of increasing the levels of microbial enzyme synthesized by classical genetic techniques, continuous culture selection, induction and optimization of growth conditions for the enzyme of interest. Diabetes is defined as a state in which homeostasis of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism is improperly regulated by the pancreatic hormone, insulin; resulting in an increased blood glucose level. Diabetes is a progressive disease and is one of the major killers in recent times. Most prevalent form of diabetes is non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM/type II). The treatment of type II diabetes is complicated by several factors inherent to the disease and elevated post prandial hyperglycemia (PPHG) is one of the risk factors . PPHG is elevated

by the action of glucosidases, a class of enzymes that helps in the breakdown of complex carbohydrates into simple sugars such as maltose and glucose. Glucosidase inhibitors such as α -amylase inhibitors plays a major role in managing PPHG in diabetic patients. These α -amylase inhibitors inhibit the action of α -amylase enzyme leading to a reduction in starch hydrolysis which shows beneficial effects on glycemic index control in diabetic patients (2002). Oxidative stress is an important risk factor in the pathogenesis of numerous chronic diseases. Free radicals and other reactive oxygen species are recognized as agents involved in the pathogenesis of sicknesses such as asthma, inflammatory arthropathies, diabetes, Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases, cancers as well as atherosclerosis. Reactive oxygen species are also said to be responsible for the human aging. An antioxidant can be broadly defined as any substance that delays or inhibits oxidative damage to a target molecule . The main characteristic of an antioxidant is its ability to trap free radicals. Antioxidant compounds like phenolic acids, polyphenols and flavonoids scavenge free radicals such as peroxide, hydroperoxide or lipid peroxy and thus inhibit the oxidative mechanisms that lead to degenerative diseases. Herbal plants considered as good antioxidant since ancient times. Rising antibiotic resistance and the scarcity of new antimicrobials has long been acknowledged. Some *Staphylococcus* spp. and *Streptococcus* spp. involved in the pathogenesis of respiratory and skin infections, along with *Pseudomonads* and members of the *Enterobacteriaceae* causing gastrointestinal, urogenital diseases and wound contamination are resistant to virtually all of the older antibiotics . Clinical isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus*, the leading cause of nosocomial infections, are increasingly resistant to an array of antimicrobial agents like penicillin, gentamicin, tobramycin, amikacin, ciprofloxacin, clindamycin, erythromycin, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole and vancomycin. The problem of antibiotic resistance in humans and animals will continue for a long time . Against this backdrop, the development of alternative drug classes to treat such infectious diseases is urgently required. Plants have an amazing ability to produce a wide variety of secondary metabolites, like alkaloids, glycosides, terpenoids, saponins, steroids, flavonoids, tannins, quinones and coumarins. These biomolecules are the source of plant-derived antimicrobial substances (PDAMs). Some natural products are highly efficient in the treatment of bacterial infections. The aim of this project is trying to use some medical plants common in ways to reduce the effectiveness of amylase and reduce the proportion of glucose blood for diabetics. And to evaluate the antioxidant activity of several

agents proposed for reversion of problems caused by bleaching procedures using the DPPH free radical assay, also to estimate the antibacterial activity and phenolic compounds of these plants extracts that might have support and help the research scientific community to study and encourage the use of medicinal plants for the treatment of diseases. The selected medical plants that used to determined α - amylase inhibition and antioxidant activity were used to measure the antibacterial activity by selected three different pathogenic bacteria included *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Enterococcus sp.* after growing on nutrient agar at 37°C for 24 h. The results shown in table that lemon has a highest antibacterial activity against *E.coli* comparison with other plants, whereas *Staph aureus* was inhibited by lemon and Garlic separately also garlic and ginger were used to inhibit the growth of *Enterococcus sp.* Lemon is an important medicinal plant of the family Rutaceae. It is a rich source of vitamin C and it is cultivated mainly for its alkaloids, which are having anticancer activities and the antibacterial potential in crude extracts of different parts (leaves, stem, root and flower) of lemon against clinically significant bacterial strains has been reported also its consists of about 5% citric acid that gives a sour (tarty) taste to the lemon found that lemon juice has the antibacterial susceptibility against some gram-positive and -negative bacterial strains. Also garlic is a potential inhibitor for food pathogens. Foods contaminated with pathogens pose a potential danger to the consumer's health. The use of garlic can increase the shelf life and decrease the possibilities of food poisoning and spoilage in processed foods. Garlic aqueous extract has antibacterial properties against *S. aureus*. In addition, garlic has antibacterial properties against other Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, which must be investigated in further studies.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, the marine *Streptomyces* isolates had the significant ability to produce industrial amylases. *Streptomyces* are considered as a worthy source for amylases, identified from mangroves. It is enormous importance as secrete extracellular amylases. The results are more virtual and low-cost production of amylase by inexpensive single media without optimization. Further study is in progress to scale up the amylase production using optimization. Therefore, the future work deals with the optimization and improvement of amylase will be explored.

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